

ISic3665

I.Sicily inscription 3665

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

sandstone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Sanctuary of the Malophoros

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Selinunte

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR113891

1. ταιοευε

2. [.]α [---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 113891

Bibliography

Gabricsi, E. 1927. Il Santuario della Malophoros a Selinunte. *Monumenti Antichi*. 32: 5-419. At 400 no.27 fig.192

Brugnone, A. 2006. Note epigrafiche selinuntine. *Thalassa*. 3: 45-123. At 45

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3665. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388932>